

CHANGES IN THE QT INTERVAL AS AN ARRHYTHMOGENIC INDICATOR DURING HEMODIALYSIS WITH A LOW LEVEL OF CALCIUM DIALYSIS SOLUTION

Murtazoev Bakhtiyor Solievich

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7882356>

Introduction. Cardiovascular pathology is the main cause of death of patients on renal replacement therapy. Calcification of the media of resistive vessels, without narrowing their lumen, disrupts their function of maintaining blood pressure in the diastole, reducing – sometimes critically – blood flow to vital organs and, first of all, to the myocardium. When rapid electrolyte shifts occurring during and after dialysis are superimposed on ischemia, the risks of severe (sometimes fatal) arrhythmias significantly increase. Large register studies have shown that mortality on dialysis is caused not only by SSP, but also in a significant part of sudden fatal SSP – and its frequency is many times higher than in the general population. In a recent DOPPS publication, 19% of deaths were attributed to sudden cardiac death, and an unspecified proportion of patients could fall into this category from the "no data" (19%) and "unknown" (8%) groups. In a recent systematic review and meta-analysis, the rate of sudden cardiac death was 3 per 100 patient-years, varying between 0.4 and 10, which partially reflects the diversity of definitions of HCV.

The progression of vascular calcification is facilitated, among other things, by constant or episodic hypercalcemia, partly determined by the level of calcium in the dialysis solution. The KDIGO2017 recommendations and the National Clinical Guidelines for MCS-CKD suggest using a dialysis solution with a calcium level from 1.25 to 1.50 mmol/l. With long-term hypercalcemia or hypocalcemia, it is recommended to change the concentration of Ca in the dialysate, since hypocalcemia leads to an acceleration of the progression of HPT, and hypercalcemia leads to increased vascular calcification. In patients with hypercalcemia, it is recommended to lower the concentration of Ca in the dialysis solution to 1.25 mmol/l. At the same time, a low level of calcium in the dialysis solution can provoke hemodynamic instability during dialysis and rhythm disturbances – during and after the session. The predictor of the latter can be the heart rate-adjusted duration of the QT interval (QTc) and its dynamics during a dialysis session.

Patients and methods. We evaluated the hemodynamic stability and the characteristics of the QT interval in one dialysis center, where all patients receive dialysis with a calcium level of 1.25 mmol/l dialysis solution for at least a year. 91 patients aged 61±12 years and the duration of HRT 68±54 months were included in the cross-sectional single-stage study.

Results. The achieved levels of correction of MCS-CKD are shown in the figure: The initial (before the session) duration of QTc was increased in 13/40 men (>440 msec) – 33% and in 10/51 women (>460 msec). Multiple logistic regression analysis as factors related to the fact of prolongation of the initial QTc, the duration of RRT (+13% risk for 1 year of treatment) and female sex (HR 3.1); When the parameters of MCN-CKD were included in the model as categorical values (according to KDIGO), the PTH range of 150-600 pg/ml was associated with a 3-fold reduction in the risk of exceeding normal QTc values compared to lower or higher levels. The change in QTc during the dialysis session was +18±54msec (p=0.003). Patients with QTc prolongation >10 msec (n=42) compared to patients without dynamics (±10 msec) (n=26) were older (63±7 v. 55±14 years (p=0.012), had less dialysis experience of

62±49 v. 92±62 months ($p=0.012$), but did not differ in the levels of calcemia and phosphatemia; in multiple logistic regression analysis, low (<150 pg/ml) and high (>600 pg/ml) PTH values were associated with QTc elongation. Seizures were observed in 41% of patients, hypotension – in 45%; 45% of patients did not show these symptoms, one of them was observed in 23%, both – in 32% of patients. Differences in the parameters of MCS-CKD in patients with and without symptoms did not reach statistical significance. The limitation of the study was its incomparable nature; it is planned to overcome this limitation in the continuation of the study.

Conclusion. Hemodialysis with a calcium level of 1.25 mmol/l in a dialysis solution is associated with an extension of the Qtc interval. The degree of elongation may depend on age, the duration of dialysis, the level of PTH and requires attention in patients receiving dialysis with low levels of calcium in the dialysis solution.

References:

1. Чепкий Л.П., Новицька-Усенко Л.В., Ткаченко Р.О. Анестезіологія та інтенсивна терапія: Підручник для ВМНЗ III–IV рівня акредитації. — К.: Вища школа, 2003. — 399 с
2. Сумин С.А. Неотложные состояния. — М.: ООО «Медицинское информационное агентство», 2005. — 752 с.
3. Ливанов Г.А., Михальчук М.А., Калмансон М.Л. Острая почечная недостаточность при критических состояниях. — СПб., 2005. — 320 с.
4. Марино П.Л. Интенсивная терапия. — М.: ГЭОТАР-Медицина, 1999. — 639 с.
5. Шейман Д.А. Патологическая физиология почек. — М.: Бином, 2007. — 206 с.